

THE HISTORY OF OLYMPIC GAMES

Nizamiddinov Saidazim

International Relations faculty “Silk Road” International University of Tourism and Cultural Heritage

Abstract: The Olympic games and sport industry suggest many opportunities for investing and improving. It is also interesting watching how the athletes during the training days prepare for the competition because it includes patience, hard work, and motivation. However, it involves some challenges that can harm the popularity of this competition or it can be connected with the tickets. These issues, incorporate the online ticket shops where some times it is hard to get because of a bad connection or old people won't be able to take it because they don't understand how to use the mobile phone and spread all over the world. In addition, there is no places in arena that's why people sometimes can't go in and they can loose their money that they paid for competition. The other problem is a crowd because people can be easily robbed their phone, wallet, and cards from bad people. The article will also discuss the history and impact of Olympic games to the world.

Key words: sport, competition, discuss, problem, people.

Introduction: Each four years, millions of people from all over the world watch the Olympic games from TV and online or sometimes they lead to buy tickets for the event. To understand, the legacy of this event usually people start to explore and learn the history from the ancient times until the modern era. While, competition is often hard for the participants they can win huge amount of money for the first place. These days, Olympic Games emerge in different countries in the world and it is beneficial for the state because it improves the tourism area. In addition, it includes many sports such as: boxing, wrestling, football, running, striking and others. People from another part of the world are able to observe it online because nowadays world is modernizing and it is accessible to watch from phone apps and TV. However, it is not easy to take part in it for the athletes because it needs hard work, patience, but in the ancient times everyone could participate. Additionally, it appeared it ancient Greece and it was the most popular peri

<https://www.xpatathens.com/living-in-athens/taste-experience/greek-philosophy-history/item/9675-a-brief-history-of-the-olympic-games>

Picture 1: this picture explains us how the winner would be rewarded as we can see in the picture it is about small crown now it is defined as a medal.

The ancient Olympic games had been established in 776BC which was started in the city named Olympia, this event was created for the ancient god ZEUS. People believed that to deserve the honor of the gods they should win the competition. It was very important for the Greek citizens therefore they were preparing so hard “it is hard for us to exaggerate how important the Olympics were for the Greeks” (Paul Christensen no data). In the period of ancient times there were a lot of wars happening and when the Olympic games started all the wars had to stop because there must be safe travelling zone for the athletes.

The most popular sport was running and there should be three marathons during the day and it was a very cruel competition because sometimes athletes lead to kill the opponent to be the winner and it was the normal situation for the people. However, it that time only man could take part in and their sisters, wife, mother couldn't come even for watching because they son or husband could die. The reason why Greek people loved sport so much because their great philosophers liked to do some sport activities and they decided to create this type of competition. Athletes had to be very good physically and they thought that every muscles must be in the best vision as possible “You need to exercise the undersole of your foot in some way. Walking in shoes meant that people's arches and the muscles in the base of the foot are not as well exercised as they may have been” (Toni Minichello no data). The most popular person who was in charge of Olympic Games was Gerakl for the Zeus and he is famous for the 12 historical feats. In 393BC competition was suddenly stopped because of the order of Theodosius. Moreover,

Olympic Games was created for improving relations and reciprocity between Greece cities. Most of the people were keen on the running sport and the winner of the sport won not only the honor but he didn't have to pay any taxes which was very hard in that time. During the Olympic games travelers and traders could earn a lot of money introducing the merchandises to the athletes and people from another cities. Although there was no enough spaces to sit and was dangerous because many people were sitting on the ground and there were snakes, scorpions, and other venomous animals.

<https://news.arizona.edu/news/olympics-then-and-now>

Picture 2: It shows us how the Olympic Games changed through the ancient time until now because in that time only man could participate but now rules were changed when women also can take part in.

The modern era of Olympic Games started in 1896 in summer which was held in Athens. There were 280 males from 12 countries and the most popular sports were cycling, swimming, gymnastic and martial arts. Nowadays, wrestling and boxing are the hardest sports and most valuable in the world, it is held every 4 years and which is happening in every part of the world. Moreover, in Olympic games there are not a lot of people who won the competition more than the two times such as: Buvaisar Saitiev (freestyle wrestling) three times champion, Michail Lopez (Greco-Roman wrestling) five times champion, Felix Savone(boxing) three times champion and many others.

As it became more popular Olympic Games created their flag, hymn, and official logo and entrepreneurs started investing money and they decided to give money and other things such as flats, cars and so on for the winners. In the ancient time if the athlete win the Olympic games 3 times government would put for them a statue and they would be buried with the honor and golds but now as it is getting more harder to win government just give for the winner a lot of money and apartments. Nowadays, Olympic games have their special opening ceremony as an international level event and the presidents try to help and provide all the needed things for their athletes. In martial arts such as boxing and wrestling they need to win the local competition inside of their cities and republics to have the opportunity to go the Olympic Stage. Olympic Games include athletes usually from 18 years old but it depends which sport because in football, players can take part in from 16 years old it depends on the skills but in martial arts it is strictly 19-20 years old. 2024 in Paris was held the Olympic games where 200 states and more could participate with more than 10 thousands athletes. National committees choose the athletes for the Olympic games and during the four years they observe the situation around the athlete and they check if there is no any problems. Most of the athletes don't want to go there and they decided to participate in the local competition or they go to the some leagues for money because it is not easy for them sportsmen should be ready not only physically but especially morally.

Conclusion: Olympic Games had created many opportunities for the athletes to win different prizes for their life. Therefore, it will be the biggest sport competition in the world as in the past and people will try to modernize it more. Sportsmen will train in another part of the world with other athletes to become stronger with the real professionals in sports for example; boxing, wrestling, football, gymnastic and other. To summarize, I think it will be helpful for the state which will held this event for investment and also for tourism

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